

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Production performance of Holstein cows at 4 stages of lactation fed 4 dietary crude protein concentrations

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Supplementary Table S1. Least square means of the interaction between stage of lactation and dietary CP levels for production performance and feed efficiency¹.

Item	Early (128 DIM)				Mid-early (162 DIM)				Mid-Late (210 DIM)				Late (282 DIM)				SE
	13.6	15.2	16.7	18.3	13.6	15.2	16.7	18.3	13.6	15.2	16.7	18.3	13.6	15.2	16.7	18.3	
BW, kg	656	637	659	660	658	660	657	663	700	684	688	698	728	734	733	727	9
BW change, kg/d	0.65	0.31	0.42	0.26	-0.16	0.18	0.38	0.44	0.22	0.15	0.37	0.55	0.32	0.96	0.79	0.77	0.208
BCS	3.15	3.11	3.04	2.99	3.21	3.06	3.12	3.10	3.26	3.30	3.25	3.26	3.32	3.40	3.47	3.47	0.08
DMI, kg/d	27.9	29.1	32.9	31.5	28.6	29.5	31.3	29.3	28.5	28.5	29.9	31.1	27.1	29.0	29.1	28.3	0.60
N intake, g/d	614	708	882	921	617	716	837	865	625	691	800	912	591	708	780	831	15
Milk yield, kg/d	42.3	43.2	48.2	48.0	39.4	40.8	44.4	41.9	34.7	38.8	40.0	41.2	29.5	30.6	33.8	26.9	1.57
FPCM ² , kg/d	40.6	41.9	48.4	47.4	39.4	40.1	43.5	41.8	36.4	40.1	40.3	40.8	31.7	31.6	35.1	28.1	1.45
Milk NEL ³ , Mcal/d	30.4	31.1	36.1	35.3	29.4	29.8	32.3	31.0	27.0	29.7	29.8	30.3	23.4	23.3	25.9	20.6	1.09
Milk composition																	
Protein, %	2.91	3.14	3.13	3.08	3.10	3.11	3.20	3.15	3.30	3.32	3.31	3.25	3.48	3.45	3.40	3.55	0.056
Fat, %	4.06	4.00	4.13	4.16	4.15	4.02	3.88	4.10	4.43	4.30	4.09	4.06	4.49	4.35	4.37	4.34	0.099
Lactose, %	4.88	4.71	4.83	4.80	4.79	4.77	4.77	4.72	4.71	4.71	4.68	4.72	4.58	4.61	4.65	4.44	0.046
MUN, mg/dL	8.6	9.2	12.4	15.3	7.8	10.0	12.1	14.6	7.7	9.9	12.4	14.0	7.9	10.3	12.6	17.1	0.359
Milk components yield																	
Protein, g/d	1,226	1,339	1,507	1,469	1,219	1,265	1,400	1,323	1,135	1,275	1,319	1,325	1,028	1,036	1,143	945	51
Fat, g/d	1,677	1,694	2,012	1,959	1,635	1,631	1,757	1,707	1,533	1,672	1,634	1,650	1,333	1,307	1,452	1,147	62
Lactose, g/d	2,060	2,045	2,328	2,298	1,890	1,947	2,124	1,985	1,642	1,827	1,876	1,955	1,356	1,415	1,561	1,216	78
Feed efficiency																	
MY/DMI ⁴	1.48	1.48	1.47	1.52	1.41	1.41	1.42	1.45	1.22	1.36	1.35	1.33	1.10	1.02	1.17	0.95	0.051
FPCM/DMI ⁵	1.44	1.45	1.48	1.50	1.39	1.38	1.40	1.43	1.28	1.42	1.36	1.32	1.18	1.07	1.21	1.00	0.047
NEL/DMI ⁶	1.07	1.07	1.10	1.12	1.03	1.02	1.04	1.06	0.95	1.05	1.00	0.98	0.87	0.79	0.89	0.73	0.035
NUE ⁷ , %	31.5	29.6	27.0	24.9	30.8	28.0	26.4	24.2	29.0	29.0	25.9	22.9	27.6	22.5	23.1	17.9	0.947

¹Dietary CP levels = 13.6, 15.2, 16.7, and 18.3% (DM basis).

²Fat-and-protein corrected milk calculated according to IDF (2015).

³Milk net energy output calculated according to NRC (2001).

⁴Milk yield (kg/d): DMI (kg/d).

⁵FPCM (kg/d): DMI (kg/d).

⁶Milk energy (Mcal/d): DMI (kg/d).

⁷Milk true protein-N: N intake × 100